

Early diagnosis of Podocytic Dysfunction and Tubulointerstitial processes with hypertension and diabetes mellitus

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Abstract: Concomitant co-occurrence of Hypertonic Disease with diabetes mellitus is a common comorbid condition in the population, and numerous scientific observations have confirmed that nephropathy is more reliable than that of any of them. Therefore, early detection of renal changes before the onset of clinical signs in these cases is of particular practical importance.

Consequently, the combination of these two common diseases and the growing number of patients with CKD associated with them will become an important medical and social problem of the XXI century.

It is known that microalbuminuria is currently the most widely used method in the early detection of nephropathy in various diseases, including Hypertonic Disease and diabetes. However, a number of morphological studies have confirmed the presence of characteristic changes in renal tissue in patients diagnosed with microalbuminuria (even, normoalbuminuria) in diabetes mellitus (31-7). Therefore, structural-functional changes in the kidney occur until microalbuminuria is detected, and therefore it is not appropriate to consider it as a test to be observed before the clinical signs of nephropathy.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, podocyte injury, microalbuminuria, glomerular basement membrane, diabetes mellitus.

Introduction. Nephrotic syndrome (NS) is one of the commonest kidney conditions to affect children and adults. It manifests as excessive leak of protein into the urine, with interstitial edema occurring through albumin loss, aggravated by salt and water retention. Moreover, secondary knock-on effects on lipid metabolism, hemostasis, and the endocrine system through loss of key binding proteins serve to augment morbidity and mortality. NS represents a heterogeneous group of conditions, some idiopathic, others with a clear genetic basis. It may be highly kidney specific, associated with extra-renal developmental malformations or occur as a complication of systemic disease. The mainstay of treatment is immunosuppression, also effective in about 8–10% of genetic cases. Non-responders generally progress to renal failure with kidney transplantation, the only life-saving treatment.

Main part. Despite the apparent heterogeneity, the unifying feature in NS is malfunction of the glomerular filtration barrier (GFB). This highly sophisticated macromolecular sieve with size and charge restricting characteristics is the primary ultra-filter of plasma by the kidney. It allows free flow of water and small solutes but restricts the passage of molecules >15 kDa; proteinuria occurs through loss of these normal permselective properties. The GFB comprises three layers: fenestrated

endothelium, glomerular basement membrane (GBM) and podocytes, specialized terminally differentiated epithelial cells connected by slit diaphragms (SD), unique intercellular junctions interposed between interdigitating foot processes (1). Endothelial cells and podocytes have a negatively charged surface glycocalyx, which together with GBM sialoproteins and heparan sulfate gives the GBM an overall negative charge at physiological pH. Although size is the primary determinant of molecular filterability, recent detection of mutations in the main component of the podocyte glycocalyx, podocalyxin, in familial NS (2) supports additional charge selection through electrostatic repulsion. Although damage to any of the three layers can result in significant proteinuria and kidney disease (3), podocytes are considered pivotal for maintaining barrier integrity. They encircle the glomerular capillaries creating a compact interdigitating network on the urinary side of the GBM. The connecting SDs integrate structural components of tight, adhesion, gap, and neuronal junctions to meet the diverse functional requirements of macromolecular filtering under high pressure while subjected to rapid changes in mechanical shear stress (4). SDs connect with the actin cytoskeleton to initiate signaling pathways that regulate podocyte function, namely plasticity of foot processes, mechanosensation, calcium flux, endocytosis, cell polarity, and cell survival. It is perhaps not surprising that podocyte gene mutations link to these key cellular functions. Podocytes also react very stereotypically to injury irrespective of whether this is acquired or resulting from an intrinsic developmental defect with reorganization of the actin cytoskeleton, foot process effacement, molecular re-characterization of SDs, apoptosis, and detachment from the GBM (5). The dramatic morphological changes correlate with dysregulation of specific markers of podocyte differentiation including WT1, PAX2, and nephrin again signify in an underlying molecular basis. Additionally, de-differentiated podocytes can attempt healing sometimes by excessive proliferation, with the eventual outcome of repair or cell death attributable to complex interplay of poorly defined genetic and epigenetic mechanisms (6–8). Clinical data support the hypothesis that the predominant cellular lesion targets podocytes; GBM gene defects usually result in insidious plasma protein leak whereas defects in podocyte/slit diaphragm genes cause precipitous leak and NS. Moreover, there is evidence for a potential role for immune regulation, particularly in childhood. Podocytes express cytokine and chemokine receptors as well as toll like receptors (TLRs) (9) and can respond to immune stimuli both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Moreover, emerging evidence indicates that podocyte injury in NS may sometimes result from an unknown circulating factor, cytokine imbalance, or immune complex injury, with rare genomic variants potentially dictating susceptibility or resistance to immune triggers and the degree of subsequent response.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is the leading cause of end stage renal disease worldwide. The increasing number of patients with diabetic chronic kidney disease (CKD) may be attributed to both type 1 and type 2 DM and explains why over 40%

of patients referred to renal replacement therapies are represented by patients with diabetic CKD[11].

Detection of podocytes in the urine of patients with type 2 DM may indicate severe injury to the podocytes, a Main component of the glomerular filtration barrier. Urinary podocytes may be a useful marker of disease activity

In diabetic nephropathy (DN), as was shown in the study by Nakamura et al. Who found podocytes in the urine Of 53% of the micro- and 80% of the macroalbuminuric patients with type 2 DM, respectively [12]. In a previous

Study we showed that urinary podocytes were present even in the or moalbuminuria stage (24% of the normoalbuminuric, 40% of the microalbuminuric, and 82% of the macroalbuminuric patients) and correlated with biomarkers of podocyte damage, nephrin and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), and with biomarkers of proximal tubule (PT) dysfunction. Podocyturia in conjunction with these biomarkers proved to be a reliable panel of diagnosis in early DN [13]. Podocyte culture, however, is a time consuming technique, rather expensive, and, although reliable for an accurate diagnosis of early renal involvement in a normoalbuminuric patient with type 2 DM, it requires an experienced cytologist [12, 14].

To date, the quantification of messenger RNA (mrna) expression in urinary sediments represents a reliable Modality for the diagnosis of early DN and for monitoring its activity and progression [15]. Thus, urinary gene Expression is considered as a potential approach to the identification of novel biomarkers in patients with DM.

According to the tubular theory concerning the mechanisms of albuminuria in the course of diabetes mellitus

Albuminuria is caused primarily by impaired tubular uptake of intact albumin rather than by an increased leakiness of the glomerular filtration barrier [16]. In previous works performed by us in normoalbuminuric patients with type 2 diabetes we demonstrated that PT dysfunction precedes the occurrence of albuminuria.

Thus, in early DN, PT dysfunction may precede glomerular injury [17, 18].

Nephrin, a transmembrane protein of the immunoglobulin superfamily, is an important component of the slit diaphragm located between the foot processes of the podocytes. The limitation of the size-selectivity of the Slit diaphragm is related to its alterations [19]. Normoalbuminuric patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes may Present with increased levels of nephrinuria, a fact which demonstrates that nephrinuria may precede microalbuminuria [20–23].

Vascular endothelial growth factor is a pro-angiogenic factor, produced mainly by the podocytes, although it May be produced by other cell types, including endothelial cells. Urinary excretion of VEGF may increase even in

The normoalbuminuria stage, a fact which suggests that urinary VEGF may be used as a sensitive biomarker in The diagnosis of early DN [23, 24].

Podocin is a 43 kda membrane-associated protein that has a hairpin structure resulting with both N- and C-terminal ends located in the cytoplasm. Podocin plays an important role in nephrin-mediated cellular signaling

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The glomerular filtration barrier and its slit diaphragm, which is a size-selective barrier between interdigitating foot processes of podocytes, are linked to the actin-based cytoskeleton by adaptive proteins, such as CD2-associated protein (CD2AP), β -catenin, and podocin [26].

CD2AP, besides its role in maintaining the structural integrity of the glomerular filtration barrier, it also plays a role as adaptive protein binding to nephrin and podocin, anchoring these proteins to actin filaments of podocyte cytoskeleton [27].

ADAM10 is a metalloproteinase which intervenes in the cleavage of L1 adhesion molecule that is regulated in the renal epithelium [28]. ADAM10 is involved in

the cleavage of growth factors, adhesion molecules, and cell surface receptors. Podocytes isolated from urines of patients with glomerular diseases express constitutively ADAM10 [29].

Alpha-actinin-4 is an actin-binding cytoskeletal protein identified in cultured mouse podocytes [30]. It plays a role in the regulation of podocyte morphology and motility, and intracellular signaling [31]. The development of

proteinuria in DN is related to cytoskeletal changes due to alterations of alpha-actinin-4 [32].

Glomerular epithelial protein 1 (GLEPP-1), also known as protein tyrosine phosphatase receptor type-O-PTPRO, is an apical-membrane-associated protein tyrosine phosphatase found in glomerular podocytes. GLEPP-1 has been examined for usage as biomarker of podocyte injury. However, PTPRO mRNA, which encodes

for GLEPP-1 has been evidenced in the urinary cells of rats with streptomycin-induced diabetes, while human studies are lacking [33].

The transcription factor NFκB helps to control the expression of various genes activated during inflammation. NFκB is induced by cell stress-associated stimuli [34], and in turn controls the regulation of genes encoding proteins involved in immune and inflammatory responses. The activation and nuclear translocation of NFκB plays an important role in DN [35].

Advanced glycation end-products (AGE) have been involved in the pathogenesis of diabetic tubulopathy in association with other multiple causative factors responsible for PT dysfunction [36].

The aim of our study was to assess the mRNA expression of podocyte-associated molecules in urinary sediment of patients with type 2 DM in relation to urinary

podocytes, to biomarkers of podocyte injury, and to biomarkers of PT dysfunction. We hypothesized that the urinary mRNA profile of podocyte-associated genes and their relationship with PT dysfunction could be under the influence of AGE, which may impact both, the glomerulus and the PT.

Conclusion. An analysis of the studied literature confirms that HD and diabetes are one of the most common comorbid cases among the population. Their coming together has been proven to lead to CKD, which is gradually damaging the kidneys and increasingly becoming a 21st century pandemic. The addition of the latter complication dramatically increases not only disability but also cardiovascular and overall mortality. Therefore, for the early detection of signs of nephropathy in this comorbid condition, the assessment of podocyte dysfunction (nephrouria) and tubulointerstitial fibrosis (aldosterone and collagen type IV) using early markers, their interaction with intrarenal hemodynamics and renal functional reserve, as well as multinational statistical methods. The study of the effect of the effectiveness of hypotensive and nephroprotective treatments is one of the current problems of medicine in the study of diseases together and separately.

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